

Notes

Inorganic Coordination Complexes. Part-V. Complexes of Divalent Zinc, Cadmium and Mercury with Substituted Salicyl Hydrazines

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As a part of our studies on metal complexes¹⁻⁶, we report here the reactions of divalent Zn, Cd and Hg with N-salicyl hydrazine (SH), N,N'-disalicyl hydrazine (DSH), N-acetyl-N'-salicyl hydrazine (ASH) and N-benzoyl-N'-salicyl hydrazine (BSH). Various substituted acyl hydrazines have been reported to coordinate through $>C=O$ and $-NH_2$ groups⁷⁻⁹, but the complexes of SH, DSH, ASH and BSH described here are of particular interest as -OH group formed by the enolization of these hydrazines provides an additional coordination site for various metal ions.

Experimental

SH was prepared by the reaction of methyl salicylate and hydrazine hydrate¹⁰⁻¹¹. ASH and BSH were obtained by acetylation and benzoilation of SH, whereas DSH was prepared by heating a mixture of methyl salicylate and SH. All ligands were further purified by repeated crystallization from hot ethanol. The complexes were prepared by the method described earlier⁴.

Results and Discussions

The insolubility of the complexes under investigation in most of the organic solvents indicated their polymeric nature¹² (cf. I, II and III). The low molar conductance values of the complexes (varying from 0.6-1.0 mhos) in pyridine showed them to be non electrolytes. All the complexes are thermally stable, as they decompose above 200° without melting.

1. *SH and DSH complexes*: The ir spectra have been interpreted on the basis of published data¹²⁻¹³. On comparing the spectra of ligands with the spectra of the complexes, a considerable negative shift of 40-60 cm^{-1} in $C=O$ stretching frequency indicates the coordination of ligands through oxygen of $C=O$ group. Coordination through nitrogen has been ruled out as δ NH mode remains unaffected. However, the negative shift of 15-25 cm^{-1} observed in the ring stretching vibrations and disappearance of OH frequency in the spectra of complexes confirm the coordination of ligand through oxygen atom of carbonyl group and oxygen of the phenolic group after deprotonation⁵. Similar ir spectral features have been observed with slight alteration in number,

position and intensity of bands in the DSH complexes.

The following polymeric structures, I and II, have been proposed for SH and DSH complexes, respectively.

I
[M = Zn, Cd, Hg]

II
[M = Zn, Cd, Hg]

2. *ASH and BSH complexes*: Ohta reported that acyl hydrazines show keto-enol tautomerism¹⁴. In view of this, ASH and BSH may exist as

The spectra of the complexes showed the negative shift of about 50 cm^{-1} in the band around 3300 cm^{-1} as compared to the spectra of the ligands showing involvement of NH group in complexation through nitrogen. An intense band in the region 1610-1670 cm^{-1} in the spectrum of ligand has been assigned to the amide I ($C=O$) mode. But in the complexes, a band is observed around 1600 cm^{-1} which suggests that the amide I band of the ligand either suffers a negative shift or disappears due to formation of $C=N$ as a result of enolization. This has been further substantiated by a band around 1500 cm^{-1} due to involvement of NCO group in complexation¹⁵. The appropriate M-N and M-O frequencies are listed in Table 1. Variation in M-N stretching frequencies of these complexes follows the "Irving Williams" order of stability of the bivalent metal complexes¹⁶ i.e. $Zn > Cd > Hg$.

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TABLE I—ANALYTICAL AND SPECTRAL DATA OF ZN, CD AND HG COMPLEXES OF SUBSTITUTED SALICYL HYDRAZINES
(Values in parenthesis are calculated)

Compounds	m.p./ Dec. Temp. °C	Colour	Metal %	C %	H %	N %	IR spectral data in cm ⁻¹			
							NH and OH	C-N, C=O	M-N	M-O
SH	144	White	—	55.02 (55.17)	5.15 (5.14)	18.20 (18.40)	3330m 3280s	1630s 1600s	—	—
Zn(SH-H) ₂	350	Dirty white	17.50 (17.71)	45.92 (45.77)	3.72 (3.81)	15.10 (15.25)	3275s	1580s 1550s	380m	430m
Cd(SH-H) ₂	250	Bright white	27.15 (27.05)	40.16 (40.57)	3.41 (3.38)	13.40 (13.52)	3280s	1575s 1550s	350m	440m
Hg(SH-H) ₂	200	White	39.68 (39.84)	33.10 (33.46)	2.62 (2.78)	11.20 (11.15)	3275s	1580s 1560s	320m	455m
DSH	302	Yellow	—	61.10 (61.25)	4.25 (4.38)	9.50 (9.69)	3300m 3100s	1610s	—	—
Zn(DSH-2H)	300	Light yellow	19.61 (19.40)	47.63 (47.32)	2.90 (2.81)	8.42 (8.35)	3100s	1560s	375m	435m
Cd(DSH-2H)	285	Yellow- ish white	29.45 (29.31)	43.43 (43.71)	2.58 (2.61)	7.30 (7.32)	3110s	1565s	340m	440m
Hg(DSH-2H)	248	Light yellow	42.35 (42.55)	35.28 (35.74)	2.01 (2.12)	5.81 (5.95)	3105s	1570s	325m	450m
ASH	183	White	—	55.86 (55.65)	5.15 (5.35)	14.70 (14.40)	3400s 3320s	1670s 1630s	—	—
Zn(ASH-2H)	400	White	25.10 (25.29)	42.21 (42.02)	3.21 (3.11)	10.75 (10.89)	3275s	1610s	370m	440m
Cd(ASH-2H)	350	White	36.68 (36.84)	35.31 (35.52)	2.52 (2.63)	9.10 (9.21)	3270s	1610s	345m	445m
Hg(ASH-2H)	200	White	51.15 (51.02)	29.35 (29.55)	2.10 (2.04)	7.05 (7.14)	3270s	1600s	320m	455m
BSH	280	White	—	65.75 (65.63)	4.96 (4.69)	10.70 (10.94)	3320s	1660s 1610s	—	—
Zn(BSH-2H)	400	Yellow- ish white	20.45 (20.37)	52.42 (52.66)	3.05 (3.13)	8.65 (8.77)	3280s	1600s	385m	435m
Cd(BSH-2H)	350	"	30.55 (30.60)	45.71 (45.90)	2.68 (2.73)	7.42 (7.65)	3285s	1605s	350m	445m
Hg(BSH-2H)	200	"	44.20 (44.05)	37.15 (37.00)	2.18 (2.20)	6.19 (6.16)	3280s	1600s	330m	450m

In view of the very poor solubility of these complexes in most of the organic solvents, the polymeric structure III may be proposed.

III
[M = Zn, Cd, Hg & R = CH₃, C₆H₅]

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